

IMPACT OF NOZZLE GEOMETRY AND INJECTION TIMING ON HCCI ENGINE OPERATED WITH MAHUA METHYL ESTER

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ABSTRACT

Homogeneous charge compression ignition (HCCI) engines can achieve high thermal efficiency with very low emissions of particulate matter and nitrogen oxides. However, managing mixture formation and combustion phasing remains a major challenge, particularly when utilizing unusual fuels. This study looks at how fuel spray angles affect the performance, combustion, and emission characteristics of an HCCI engine running on Mahua and Jamun methyl esters. The trials were conducted using a single-cylinder, four-stroke compression ignition engine that had been modified to operate in HCCI mode by changing spray angles under constant engine speed and load conditions. Exhaust emissions and brake thermal efficiency were investigated in relation to the multi-hole common rail direct injection injector with a narrow spray angle of 60° and a conventional spray angle of 156°.

KEYWORDS: HCCI engine, Mahua methyl ester, Spray angle, Multi-hole Fuel Injector.

INTRODUCTION

Since the invention of the internal combustion engine, the automotive industry has relied heavily on fossil fuels, resulting in a discrepancy between the production and consumption of fossil fuels. Additionally, compared to alternative fuels, gasoline engines provide more energy with less pollutants, and these internal combustion engines emit a variety of hazardous substances into the environment [1,2]. A hybrid power system, which combines the advantages of an internal combustion engine with those of an electric vehicle, is the best solution to this problem. The development of hybrid cars aims to increase power, reduce emissions, and improve fuel economy. Hybrid electric vehicles still rely on traditional internal combustion engines, despite the fact that they can significantly reduce environmental pollution [3,4]. Electrification and hybridization should remove several barriers to public transportation use. Hybrid electric vehicles are more efficient and environmentally friendly thanks to advanced combustion principles like low-temperature combustion. This more current engine technology reduces nitrogen oxide and soot emissions while increasing thermal efficiency [5,6]. Modern fuel injection, variable valve timing, and exhaust gas recirculation technology enable this kind of combustion. Although low-temperature combustion is the best solution to the current vehicle emissions problems, it has certain disadvantages. Conventional power transmission's short operational range is its main drawback. By adding an electric motor to the transmission, this problem is fixed and the motor's operating range is increased [7,8]. In this case, hybrid electric vehicles can be helpful since they combine a low-temperature internal combustion engine with an electric motor transmission system, which increases the power range and permits faster speeds. This study mainly focuses on two types of low-temperature combustion, while there are other varieties. compression ignition with controlled reactivity and direct injection of a constant charge. After the fuel and oxidizer have been thoroughly mixed and compressed, diesel fuel is instantly fed into a direct injection homogeneous fuel unit to begin burning. Two fuels — one highly reactive and the other not are used in a reactivity-controlled compression ignition system. Low reactivity gasoline does not ignite on its own even though it is squeezed. When highly reactive fuel is added at the end of the compression stroke, the mixture is fully ignited [9–12].

FUELS USED FOR THE STUDY

The fuels used in the study are discussed in this chapter. These fuels are compatible to diesel engine as they exhibit desirable physico-chemical properties such as good combustion quality, good oxidation, thermal stability and higher energy density. In the present work, biodiesel of mahua seed oil called MAHUAOB B20 was used as pilot fuel. It has been determined how the aforementioned fuel mixtures affect the HCCI engine's performance, emissions and combustion.

Table-1. Properties of Diesel, MAHUAOB B20

Properties	Diesel	MAHUAOB B20
Density (kg/m ³)	830	840
Calorific value (kJ/kg)	43,000	38,206
Flashpoint (°C)	54	128
Kinematic Viscosity (cSt)	2.3	3.32

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The current one-cylinder, four-stroke, water-cooled, direct injection, compression ignition conventional engine with a 5.2 kW capacity at 1500 rpm serves as the foundation for the common rail direct injection engine test rig. Figure-1 shows the complete HCCI engine test rig with necessary accessories. Engine specifications are provided in Table-2. Figure-2 shows Chamber and fuel spray (a) Conventional diesel engine. (b) Modified engine configurations for prior injection.

Figure-1. HCCI engine test rig

Figure-2. Chamber and fuel spray (a) Conventional diesel engine. (b) Modified engine configurations for prior injection

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure-3. Effect of injection timing, single and multi-hole injector on brake thermal efficiency of HCCI engine

Figure-3 shows effect of injection timing, single and multi-hole injector on brake thermal efficiency of HCCI engine. The brake thermal efficiency showed falling trend with advancement in fuel injection timing from 35 to 80° bTDC. Single-hole injectors spray fuel axially, which minimizes spray falling on the cylinder wall and ensures better combustion with a higher brake thermal efficiency than multi-hole injectors. Because of the lower heat release rate, HCCI operation with MAHUA B20 and a lowered spray angle of 60° produced higher brake thermal efficiency than conventional injector. For single and

multi-hole injectors, the brake thermal efficiency of an HCCI engine running on MAHUA B20 at an IT of 55° bTDC is determined to be 9.5%, 18.78% and 17.75% respectively.

Figure-4. Impact of injection timing, single and multi-hole injectors on HCCI engine smoke emissions

Figure-4 shows effect of injection timing, single and multi-hole injector on smoke emissions of HCCI engine. For advanced injection timing, HCCI operation led to reduce smoke opacity. Initial fuel injection created a homogenous fuel-air combination, enhanced combustion and decreased smoke emissions. Due to better combustion, HCCI with a multi-hole injector formed more smoke than a single injector. Single hole injector ensures homogeneous air-fuel mixture formation with enhanced combustion. Smoke of the HCCI with MAHUA B20 at injection timing of 55° bTDC for single and multi-hole injectors is found to be 18 HSU, 22 HSU and 26 HSU respectively.

Figure-5. Effect of injection timing, single and multi-hole injector on hydrocarbon emissions of HCCI engine

Figures 5 and 6 show how injection timing affects hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emissions of the HCCI engine at 60% load. As the fuel injection timing was advanced to 80° bTDC, the engine's emissions of both hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emissions rise. Cylinder wall and piston bowl wetness may be the cause of the trend that has been noticed. The HCCI operation with multi-hole injector yielded higher hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emissions as compared to single hole injector because of lowered brake thermal efficiency. Because of the improved brake thermal efficiency and uniform air-fuel mixture generation, a multi-hole injector with a smaller spray angle produced fewer hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emissions than a traditional injector. For single and multi-hole injectors, the hydrocarbon emissions of HCCI engine running on MAHUA B20 at injection timing of 55° bTDC is 810 ppm, 840 ppm, and 870 ppm, respectively. The carbon monoxide emissions of HCCI engine fueled with MAHUA B20 at injection timing of 55° bTDC for single and multi-hole injectors is found to be 0.12%, 0.15% and 0.18 % respectively.

Impact of fuel injection timing on nitric oxide emissions at 60% load is depicted in Figure-7. For advanced fuel injection timing, the HCCI operation was associated with a decrease in engine nitric oxide. Lower combustion temperatures inside combustion chamber with controlled heat release rate may be the cause of the trend that has been observed. The oxides of nitrogen emissions from HCCI operation with a multi-hole injector were heightened than from a single-hole injector. However, due to improved brake thermal efficiency, a multi-hole injector with a lower spray angle of 60° produced more nitric oxide emissions than a typical multi-hole injector. At an injection timing of 55° bTDC, the nitric oxide emissions of the HCCI engine running on MAHUA B20 for single and multi-hole injectors are 110 ppm, 146 ppm, and 136 ppm, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The cool flame responses of HCCI operation, were seen in the injection timing of 35° bTDC, when HCCI operation begins. Compared to multi-hole injectors at 60% engine load conditions, single-hole injector HCCI operation with MAHUA B20 at injection timing of 55° bTDC demonstrated higher brake thermal efficiency and poorer smoke, hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emissions. Related to traditional multi-hole injector, a multi-hole injector with a smaller spray cone angle demonstrated good efficacy with brake thermal efficiency and fewer emissions.

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